

STATISTICAL ASPECTS OF TENSILE STRENGTH OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS*

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Abstract

A model for composite materials is presented and exact analytical results are obtained for small bundles. Numerical results are plotted for purposes of describing size effect, upper and lower tail behaviors of the strength distribution, and weakest link features of composites. Strong numerical evidence of convergence of the strength distribution is presented in support of a weakest link transformation whereby results for smaller composites can be rescaled to apply to large composites. For practical purposes the Weibull distribution may be used to represent composite strength. Using a specific example, it is shown that the Weibull shape and scale parameters obtained by numerical means agree well with those obtained by experimental means.

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Introduction

The simplest composite material is a bundle of parallel fibers impregnated with a binding matrix. Tensile failure of such composites under axial tension is known to have statistical features, and probability models have been proposed to explain these features. In the best known probability model, the composite is considered to be a chain of m short bundles each with n fibers of length δ , the ineffective length. Therefore, the composite length is $l = m\delta$. The primary objective is to describe the probability distribution for the tensile strength in order to explain scatter and size effect. The ideal result would be a simple analytical expression for the strength distribution, scatter or size effect; however, experience has proven that this is impossible, the reason being the tremendous complexity of the failure process in the model for the composite. Even with assumptions, which are overly restrictive in reflecting the true failure mechanism but which are introduced to reduce the complexity to manageable proportions, previous investigators have had limited success in computing the probability of failure. Consequently, a direct approach making only basic assumptions which are fundamental to composite failure is the most productive avenue.

In the "chain-of-bundles" probability model, the description of bundle failure is critical. The basic assumption is that each bundle is constrained by a local load sharing (LLS) rule describing the failure process. By theoretical and experimental means it has been established that for realistic material properties and geometry, the immediate lateral neighbors to a single broken fiber bear most of the shifted load, the second nearest neighbors bear a small fraction of the shifted load, and more distant neighbors bear increasingly negligible amounts. However, for several broken fibers in a lateral row, the more distant neighbors carry a significant fraction of the shifted load. Evidently, the exact values of the load shift factors depend on the elastic and plastic properties of the matrix, on the strength of the fiber matrix interfact, and on the fiber spacing. Furthermore, the magnitude of the overload effect on neighboring fibers decays in the longitudinal direction within a few fiber diameters away from the break, and the profile of the decay depends strongly on the mechanical properties of the matrix and fiber spacing. To accurately describe this process analytically is a formidable task, and restrictions are necessary if any results are to be obtained. Thus, it is assumed that the fibers in a bundle are arranged in a circular array with uniform spacing and that the immediate lateral neighbors to broken fibers bear all of the shifted load. Except for assumptions inherent

in these constraints, no further restrictions are placed on the failure mechanism.

The first and most difficult task is to study this mathematical structure. Cumbersome but exact results are obtained for small bundles. These results give rise to several interesting conclusions.

The second task, which is extremely important, is to analyze the graphical results of a careful numerical investigation of the model. The computational complexity becomes overwhelming even for bundles and composites with 10 parallel fibers; therefore, numerical results were only obtained for bundles with nine or fewer fibers. Nevertheless, these results are very important because a technique was discovered which allows these results to be extended to composites with a large number of fibers. The technique discovered and the conclusive numerical evidence supporting its validity are believed to be the most important aspects of this study.

Reflecting upon previous studies, certain features associated with composite failure and composite strength must be considered. The more important features to be appraised are the behavior of the probability distribution of strength, "size-effect characteristics, the relationship between fiber strength which has high scatter and a high mean and composite strength which has low scatter and a lower mean, and "weakest link" characteristics of composite failure. Each of these is discussed in this paper.

The most significant conclusion is that by using a weakest link transformation distributions of bundle strength converge rapidly to a limit as bundle size increases over a broad range of probabilities varying from 10^{-10} to .9999. This allows for the estimation of strength in large bundles (up to 10^9 fibers) by using the results of small bundles. Simple graphical procedures are given to implement this estimation. Secondly, it is shown, using a typical example, that for practical purposes a Weibull distribution may be used to represent composite strength, but the shape and scale parameters differ from those for single fibers. Finally, the numerical results indicate that, in support of experimental observations, variability in composite strength is much less than that for individual fibers, and as the variability in fiber strength increases, bundle and composite strength greatly decrease.

Development of the Model

The class of composites considered in this study is that class in which a low stiffness matrix is reinforced by high-strength and high-stiffness fibers aligned in parallel. Most investigators agree on several random

features of the tensile failure process for composites. The randomness arises from the fibers which display much variability in tensile strength. This variability is a result of either internal or external flaws randomly distributed along each fiber. When the composite is loaded in the axial direction, isolated breaks occur in fibers at loads well below the composite failure load. As the load is increased, breaks accumulate until composite failure results. Some breaks occur as a result of initial loading, and some breaks occur as a result of overloading. The complex nature of composite failure is manifest.

The widely accepted assumption for composite materials is that the "chain-of-bundles" probability model is appropriate. Each bundle, having length δ , called the ineffective length, consists of n fiber segments. If the composite has length $l = m\delta$, then m is the number of bundles in the chain. The range of m is from 10 in short laboratory specimens to more than 10^6 in cables. Hence, asymptotic results for long composites are desired. The loads supported by each nonfailed fiber in a bundle sum to equal the axial load supported by the composite, of course assuming that failed fibers support no load. For each bundle the loads assigned to nonfailed fibers are determined for each distinct arrangement of failed and nonfailed fibers by a prescribed load sharing rule.

While agreeing on features of the model just described, previous investigators differ in their description of the load sharing rule. Gücer and Gurland [1], Rosen [2], and Scop and Argon [3] assumed that the equal load sharing rule, which implies that in each bundle the surviving fibers equally share the total load, introduced and developed by Daniels [4], would be applicable for composites. Weaknesses in this rule were soon exposed, and Zweben [5], Zweben and Rosen [6], Scop and Argon [7] turned to more realistic local load sharing rules. While their analysis helped to clarify statistical aspects of the failure mechanism of composites, serious gaps persisted in their models, as acknowledged by the authors themselves. One serious shortcoming was a vague description of the load sharing rule so that it is impossible to analytically describe every possible situation which can arise in bundle failure. This necessarily means that their values for the probability of failure, if these can be obtained, are approximations. Possibly the most serious fault was that additional assumptions, not warranted by physical considerations, were imposed on the pattern of the failure of fibers in each bundle. Consequently the results they obtained are approximations of unknown proximity to exact results.

There are two crucial aspects of a load sharing rule. One is the precise description of how much load each nonfailed fiber must support, and the

second aspect, which influences the first, is that of the geometrical structure of the composite. In this study it is assumed that the fibers are arranged in a circular array with uniform spacing. This geometry is simple enough so that a complete description of failure progression in a bundle can be made; yet, the belief is that the key features of composite failure for any geometrical structure is captured by this situation. The measure of how much load a nonfailed fiber supports is contained in the load concentration factors. Let r be the number of broken fibers immediately adjacent to an unbroken fiber, then the load concentration factor for the unbroken fiber will be $K_r = 1 + r/2$. Naturally, if there is only one survivor, it supports the whole load. No pretense is made that this local load sharing rule (LLS rule) is more realistic than those rules used by other investigators. This rule does satisfy the simple constraints required by bundle failure. Moreover, the advantage of this LLS rule is that every possible configuration of failed and nonfailed fibers can be described whereas none of the previous attempts come close to describing all configurations. The values of K_r for the LLS rule are slightly larger than those typically used for two dimensional structures. This has the effect of yielding slightly more conservative values for the probability of failure. The major advantage is that the model under this load sharing rule allows for exact analysis for composite failure, and hence it is an improvement over any incomplete analysis.

Along with the above physical structure of the model, the mathematical structure must be developed. The strengths of the fibers in a bundle are assumed to be independent and identically distributed random variables with distribution function given by

$$F(x) = 1 - e^{-(x/x_0)^\rho}, \quad x \geq 0 \quad (1)$$

where x_0 and ρ are the scale and shape parameters respectively for the Weibull distribution. The major task is to determine the distribution for bundle strength $G_n(x)$ and the distribution for composite strength $H_{m,n}(x)$, where x is load per fiber. Since the "chain-of-bundles" probability model is assumed and bundle strengths are independent, then the relation between $G_n(x)$ and $H_{m,n}(x)$ is given by

$$H_{m,n}(x) = 1 - [1 - G_n(x)]^m, \quad x \geq 0. \quad (2)$$

For large m , the lower tail behavior of $G_n(x)$ governs the behavior of $H_{m,n}(x)$ in the range of strength values of interest. Thus the critical task is not only to compute $G_n(x)$ for typical values of x , but also to compute

the lower tail of $G_n(x)$ with sufficient accuracy that $H_{m,n}(x)$ may be obtained. Zweben [5] and Zweben and Rosen [6] were unable to obtain an expression for $G_n(x)$. Scop and Argon [7] obtained an expression for $G_n(x)$ under additional assumptions alluded to earlier. Unfortunately their expression for $G_n(x)$ exceeds one for some values of x and $G_n(x)$ approaches zero as x approaches infinity. Their expression violates two of the fundamental properties of a distribution function. Nevertheless, their expression gives several key insights into the proper behavior of composite failure.

Consider one bundle, and let the random variable X_i be the strength of fiber i , and assume that X_1, \dots, X_n are independent and identically distributed with distribution function $F(x)$ given in (1). Let Z_n be the strength of the bundle on a per fiber basis, that is, Z_n is the total load the bundle will support divided by the number of fibers in the bundle n . Now the stage is set so that $G_n(x)$ can be computed.

As an example, consider a 4-fiber bundle. This is the simplest case which differs from the classical work done by Daniels [4]. In Figure 1 all the states, given as vectors, of failed and nonfailed fibers are listed. The vector components are the associated load concentration factors. Considering circular symmetries there are only six different states.

Figure 1. All states of failed and surviving fibers for a 4-fiber bundle under the Local Load Sharing Rule. The components of the vectors are the associated load factors.

Suppose a load x per fiber is applied to the bundle. Failure occurs if the fiber strengths permit a progression starting in state a and continuing to state p . For example if $X_1 \leq x$, $x < X_2 \leq 3x/2$, $2x < X_3 \leq 4x$, $3x/2 < X_4 \leq 2x$, then failure occurs by way of $a \rightarrow b \rightarrow f \rightarrow n \rightarrow p$. Since a fiber cannot repair itself and if a fiber can support a load of $K_r x$ at one stage, it will fail only under an increase in load, then certain transitions are impossible. To illustrate these restrictions, a transition from b to c is impossible, and a transition from b to g is impossible. Computation of $G_4(x)$ involves calculating and summing the probabilities of all feasible failure sequences. The probability for the above example is

$$F(x)[F(3x/2) - F(x)][F(2x) - F(3x/2)][F(4x) - F(2x)].$$

For further clarification, the following list is a few more examples of feasible failure sequences with their associated probability of failure:

$$a \rightarrow b \rightarrow n \rightarrow p \quad \text{w.p.} \quad F(x)[F(3x/2) - F(x)]^2[F(4x) - F(x)],$$

$$a \rightarrow f \rightarrow n \rightarrow p \quad \text{w.p.} \quad F(x)^2[F(2x) - F(x)][F(4x) - F(2x)],$$

$$a \rightarrow o \rightarrow p \quad \text{w.p.} \quad F(x)^3[F(4x) - F(x)],$$

and

$$a \rightarrow p \quad \text{w.p.} \quad F(x)^4.$$

An exact expression can be obtained by the above description for $G_4(x)$, and it is found to be

$$\begin{aligned} G_4(x) = & 16F(4x)F(2x)F\left(\frac{3}{2}x\right)F(x)^2 - 4F(4x)F(2x)F(x)^2 \\ & - 4F(4x)F\left(\frac{3}{2}x\right)^2F(x) + 4F(4x)F(x)^3 - 8F(2x)^2F\left(\frac{3}{2}x\right)F(x) \\ & + 2F(2x)^2F(x)^2 - 8F(4x)F\left(\frac{3}{2}x\right)F(x)^2 + 4F\left(\frac{3}{2}x\right)^2F(x)^2 - F(x)^4. \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

As the number of fibers increases the exact expression for $G_n(x)$ becomes more difficult to obtain. In general there are 2^n states of failed and nonfailed fibers, and the number of feasible failure sequences likewise grows very large. To demonstrate this difficulty, the expression for $G_5(x)$ is given,

$$\begin{aligned}
G_5(x) = & 40F(5x)F\left(\frac{5}{2}x\right)F(2x)F\left(\frac{3}{2}x\right)F(x) - 10F(5x)F\left(\frac{5}{2}x\right)F(2x)F(x)^2 \\
& - 10F(5x)F\left(\frac{5}{2}x\right)F\left(\frac{3}{2}x\right)^2F(x) - 10F(5x)F(2x)^2F\left(\frac{3}{2}x\right)F(x) \\
& + 5F(5x)F(2x)^2F(x)^2 + 10F(5x)F(2x)F(x)^3 \\
& - 30F(5x)F(2x)F\left(\frac{3}{2}x\right)F(x)^2 + 5F(5x)F\left(\frac{3}{2}x\right)^2F(x)^2 \\
& + 10F(5x)F\left(\frac{3}{2}x\right)F(x)^3 - 5F(5x)F(x)^4 \\
& - 20F\left(\frac{5}{2}x\right)^2F(2x)F\left(\frac{3}{2}x\right)F(x) + 5F\left(\frac{5}{2}x\right)^2F(2x)F(x)^2 \\
& + 5F\left(\frac{5}{2}x\right)^2F\left(\frac{3}{2}x\right)^2F(x) + 5F(2x)F\left(\frac{3}{2}x\right)^2F(x)^2 - 5F(2x)^2F(x)^3 \\
& + 10F(2x)^2F\left(\frac{3}{2}x\right)F(x)^2 - 5F\left(\frac{3}{2}x\right)^2F(x)^3 + F(x)^5. \tag{4}
\end{aligned}$$

Notice that there are twice as many terms as in (3) and each term has an additional multiplicative factor. Because this trend continues, manual computation is prohibitive for n greater than 6. Unfortunately no simple expression or recursion has been observed for $G_n(x)$ even for bundle sizes of $1, \dots, 6$. Undoubtedly the unyielding geometrical dependence in the composite failure process makes it impossible to obtain exact but simple expressions for $G_n(x)$.

As an aside, an alternate approach to the one given using order statistics can be used to compute $G_4(x)$. The expressions obtained are identical to (3) and (4). For details see Harlow [8].

To circumvent the manual labor needed to compute $G_4(x)$, a computer algorithm was generated to compute $G_4(x)$ which mimics the approach described in the above discussion. Due to time and cost, the direct algorithm used to compute $G_n(x)$ is impractical to use for bundles with more than nine fibers. The reason is that the number of feasible failure sequences grows very large even for relatively small n . The following list shows the increase in feasible failure sequences:

<u>n</u>	<u>feasible failure sequences</u>
1	1
2	3
3	13
4	51
5	221
6	963
7	4,285
8	19,267
9	87,421

Having exact results only for bundles with nine or less fibers is no real handicap since a technique was discovered whereby exact results for small bundles can be rescaled to give results for large bundles.

Computation of $G_n(x)$ was performed using double precision accuracy, 16 digits. From a crude bound of the computational error, there were more than five significant digits generated by the computer algorithm for $G_9(x)$. For n less than nine, the accuracy is better. Thus, the values obtained are significant far above graphical resolution.

Discussion of Numerical Results

In all calculations $F(x)$, the strength distribution for a fiber, was assumed to be the Weibull distribution (1). Notice that $F(x)$ may be rewritten in terms of the dimensionless load variable x/x_0 , because x_0 is simply a scale parameter. Similarly, each distribution function which is dependent upon $F(x)$ will be in terms of x/x_0 , henceforth called the load.

Weibull probability paper was chosen to display all numerical results because of its advantages. One advantage is that the lower tail portion of a distribution is clearly displayed. Another advantage is that a true Weibull distribution is linear on Weibull probability paper so that deviation from Weibull behavior for plotted distributions are easily observed. Possibly the most important advantage is that Weibull probability paper allows easy calculation of the distribution of a chain of elements given the plotted distribution for a single element. To see this let $J(x)$ be the distribution function for an element, and let $J_n(x)$ be the distribution function for a chain of n elements. Thus,

$$J_n(x) = 1 - [1 - J(x)]^n.$$

The vertical scale is linear in $\ln(-\ln[1 - p(x)])$, and the horizontal scale is linear in $\ln(x)$ for Weibull probability paper. Since

$$\ln(-\ln[1 - J_n(x)]) = \ln(n) + \ln(-\ln[1 - J(x)]), \quad (5)$$

then $J_n(x)$ is just $J(x)$ translated vertically the amount $\ln(n)$ with no change in shape. Given the distribution function for bundle strength $G_n(x)$, it is simple to obtain the graph of the distribution function of composite strength $H_{m,n}(x)$; $H_{m,n}(x)$ is $G_n(x)$ translated upward $\ln(m)$ units. Finally, by rotating the Weibull paper counterclockwise 90° a graph of the median of the strength of the chain versus chain length m is generated.

The horizontal axis is merely relabeled to be linear in $\ln(m)$ with $\ln(1)$ centered at the previous 0.5 probability level.

The first results to be considered are contained in Figure 2. These numerical results were obtained using the exact analysis described earlier. Figure 2 is a display of $G_8(x)$ obtained by using Daniels [4] classical model with equal load sharing (ELS), and by using the local load sharing (LLS) model of this paper. Also displayed are $F(x)$ for a single fiber and $F_8(x)$ the distribution function for a chain of eight fibers. The important features of this graph are common to those with other values of n and ρ , the Weibull shape parameter for $F(x)$, and hence Figure 2 is an excellent prototype.

Figure 2. Probability distributions for an 8-fiber bundle under equal load sharing (ELS) and local load sharing (LLS) with upper and lower tail asymptotes.

Several observations are manifest. First, there is a substantial difference between G_8 under ELS and G_8 under LLS. This confirms the fact that the classical model is not adequate for modeling composite failure. The difference becomes even more pronounced for larger bundles. Secondly, the upper regions of G_8 under both load sharing rules are asymptotic to F_8 which is Weibully distributed with shape parameter ρ equal to five and scale parameter equal to $x_0 8^{-1/5}$. This is intuitive because for high loads the bundle will fail whenever the weakest fiber fails regardless of the load sharing, and thus at high loads weakest link behavior results. Thirdly, for low loads G_8 lies well below F implying that the bundle is considerably better than a single fiber. Notice that the lower tail of G_8 , for both load sharing rules, appears to be approaching a straight line with a slope much greater than the slope of F . In a study to be reported on later, Taylor, Smith, and Harlow [9] have proven that for x near zero

$$G_n(x) = (x/x_{0,n}^*)^{n\rho} + o(x^{n\rho}) \quad (6)$$

for some constant $x_{0,n}^*$ and for all n . The appropriate value of $x_{0,8}^*$ was obtained and $(x/x_{0,8}^*)^{8\rho}$ was plotted. Note from the graph that the probability must be extremely small in order for this to be a useful bound. With respect to size effect for the strength of an 8-fiber bundle and the associated composite, it is clear that both the bundle and the composite are weaker in median strength than a single fiber segment. Also, at higher loads the single fiber is superior. The median strength is 0.65 for the LLS model and 0.68 for the ELS model. The variability in composite strength steadily decreases as the length m increases because of the downward curvature of the tail of $G_n(x)$, and for x near zero the coefficient of variation for $H_{m,8}$ approaches that of a Weibull distribution with a shape parameter of $8\rho = 40$ which is 0.0314.

The next set of numerical results to be considered give rise to the most important conclusions of this study. Many interesting characteristics of composite failure are observed from the careful analysis of the model for small numbers of fibers; however, the question of utmost importance which remains to be answered is how do large composites behave. For large composites engineers often assume weakest link behavior and use the Weibull distribution for the strength where the scale and shape parameter are estimated experimentally by data from smaller laboratory specimens. This practical approach fortunately leads to very useful conclusions when it is preformed properly.

So that weakest link features of $G_n(x)$ and $H_{m,n}(x)$ could be readily observed, as n increases, the following quantity was plotted on Weibull probability paper:

$$W_n(x) = 1 - [1 - G_n(x)]^{1/n} \quad (7)$$

Thus $W_n(x)$ is a weakest link scaling of $G_n(x)$, for an n-fiber bundle, back to single fiber size. On Weibull probability paper $W_n(x)$ is $G_n(x)$ translated downward the amount $\ln(1/n)$.

A typical example of $W_n(x)$ as n increases is given in Figure 3. Several observations are apparent. For a Weibull shape parameter $\rho = 5$ the coefficient of variation for fiber strength is 0.229 which is rather large. Yet even in this case the self-evident convergence is quite remarkable. The plots of W_n differ an insignificant amount for n greater than four in the probability region above 10^{-4} . For n greater than six the plots are identical for probabilities above 10^{-8} . Hence, the convergence appears to be extremely rapid in the upper portion of the distribution and is rather rapid in the extreme lower portion. Notice also that Weibull probability paper exaggerates the differences in W_n because the lower tails are emphasized. The indicated convergence is even more striking for larger values of ρ . For $\rho = 10$ the coefficient of variation for fiber strength is 0.1203 which is a typical value, and the graphs of W_n are virtually identical for n greater than four in the probability range above 10^{-10} . For $\rho = 15$, which implies that the coefficient of variation is 0.0818, the graphs of W_n were indistinguishable for n greater than three for probabilities above 10^{-10} .

These numerical results overwhelmingly indicate that there is a limiting distribution function $W(x)$ to which $W_n(x)$ converges as n increases. The remarkable result is that the convergence is practically complete for $n = 9$ which is advantageous because computation time and costs are prohibitive for n greater than nine. This evidence does not constitute a rigorous mathematical proof of the convergence. Thus, the proof of convergence, which appears to be a rather difficult task, remains as an open conjecture.

The above numerical results suggest that under the LLS model large bundles act in a weak link manner. Rewriting (7) gives

$$G_n(x) = 1 - [1 - W_n(x)]^n. \quad (8)$$

Since $W_n(x)$ changes insignificantly for n greater than eight for values of ρ and x in applications, then (8) can be used for large bundles. Figure 4 is a graph of W_9 , conjectured to be approximately W_∞ , for Weibull shape parameter values of $\rho = 3, 5, 7, 10, 15, 25$, and 50. To obtain G_n the graph is simply translated vertically the amount $\ln(n)$. For example, for $n = 10^6$, $G_{10^6}(x)$ can be obtained for probability levels above 10^{-4} .

Figure 3. Convergence of the transformed probability distribution for bundle strength as bundle size increases. Local load sharing (LLS) is assumed.

Hence, as the bundle size increases knowledge of the lower tail behavior is sacrificed. Figure 4 is only useful for single bundles with less than 10^9 fibers.

Combining (2) and (8) yields

$$H_{m,n}(x) = 1 - [1 - W_n(x)]^{mn}. \quad (9)$$

Thus, for composites with more than nine fibers the strength distribution can be obtained from Figure 4 by translating the amount $\ln(mn)$. Again, the value of the weakest link transformation and the implied convergence is manifest. To obtain $H_{m,n}(x)$ for n less than nine, (2) may be used directly with exact results for $G_n(x)$.

Figure 4. Conjectured limit for the transformed distribution of bundle strength as bundle size n increases (actual results for $n = 9$).

A Practical Application

Engineers frequently use the Weibull distribution for the tensile strength distribution of composite materials. The shape and scale parameter are estimated from experimental data. Using an example, support for this practice is given, and other conclusions are discussed which also substantiate experimental observations from composites.

Recalling (9) and the numerical evidence of the convergence of $W_n(x)$ to $W_\infty(x)$, it is clear that $H_{m,n}(x)$ depends upon mn which is the total number of fiber segments in a composite. In other words, the total volume mn is the controlling factor in size effect of composites rather than just length or width.

For the example, assume that $mn = 10^6$ which is realistic for laboratory

specimens. Figure 5 is obtained from Figure 4 by translating the graphs vertically, the amount $\ln(10^6)$. For the given values of ρ , the graphs of $H_{m,n}(x)$ are almost linear. This implies that $H_{m,n}(x)$ is for practical purposes Weibully distributed. Let

$$F_c(x) = 1 - e^{-mn(x/x_{0c})^{\rho_c}}, \quad x \geq 0, \quad (10)$$

where ρ_c and x_{0c} are composite shape and scale parameters respectively. Thus

$$H_{m,n}(x) \approx F_c(x) \quad (11)$$

for suitable values of ρ_c and x_{0c} . Notice that slopes of the lines in Figure 5 change slowly as ρ is increased. In fact, the effective Weibull shape parameter ρ_c varies from approximately 25 to 50, a twofold increase, as the Weibull shape parameter for the fiber ρ varies from 5 to 50, a tenfold increase. Also observe that the ratio of variability in fiber strength to variability in composite strength decreases. It is also possible to compare the effective scale parameter x_{0c} with the scale parameter of a fiber x_0 by using Figure 5. As ρ ranges from 5 to 50, x_{0c} ranges from $0.51x_0$ to $1.01x_0$, and for a typical value of ρ , say 10, for the fiber, $x_{0c} \approx 0.63x_0$ and $\rho_c \approx 35$ for the composite. These estimates of the Weibull behavior of $H_{m,n}(x)$ are conservative in increasing mn because the graphs of $H_{m,n}(x)$ in Figure 5 actually increase in slope with decreasing probability levels. This example is very typical of experimental data, and thus it supports the use of a Weibull approximation for composite strength.

Conclusions

The results contained in this paper are for one specialized local load sharing rule and one type of fiber configuration. Both heuristical and numerical evidence indicates that this special case is characteristic of composite tensile failure in general. For different variations in local load sharing and geometrical structures the convergence of $W_n(x)$ will probably be somewhat slower. The proof of the conjectured convergence, whether in the special case or in general, appears to be difficult, and new insight is needed for this task.

Figure 5. Distributions of strength for composite specimens of typical laboratory dimensions under local load sharing (LLS).

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